

VETERINARY SCIENCES

STATE OF INTESTINAL MICROBIOCENOSIS AND BIOCHEMICAL BLOOD PARAMETERS OF CHICKENS UNDER FEEDING WITH FEED CONTAMINATED BY BIOTIC FACTORS AND THE USE OF CAMBRIAN CLAY

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Abstract

The effect of Cambrian clay on productive performance, intestinal microbiocenosis, and biochemical blood parameters of chickens under feeding with low-toxic feed was investigated. It was established that feeding low-toxic feed resulted in a 23.2% decrease in body weight, a 3.06-fold reduction in average daily gain, and a 1.59-fold deterioration in feed conversion. Chickens developed intestinal dysbiosis accompanied by an increase in opportunistic microorganisms and suppression of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. Biochemical alterations were characterized by a 12.9% decrease in total protein and a 22.2% decrease in globulins, as well as a 57.8% increase in cholesterol concentration and a 60.0% increase in ALT activity. The use of Cambrian clay improved productive performance, partially normalized intestinal microbiocenosis, and stabilized the biochemical status of chickens, indicating the prospects of its use as a natural enterosorbent in poultry farming.

Keywords: *Bifidobacterium*, *Candida albicans*, *Clostridium*, dysbiosis, *Enterosorbents*, microbiota, mycotoxins, chickens, toxic feed.

Introduction

One of the most pressing problems in modern poultry farming remains the contamination of grain raw materials by biotic factors, particularly microscopic fungi and their secondary metabolites — mycotoxins. According to recent meta-analyses, more than 70% of grain feed samples simultaneously contain several types of mycotoxins, the combined effects of which lead to intestinal dysbiosis, disruption of epithelial barrier integrity, and severe metabolic disorders in poultry [1, 2].

Mycotoxins are toxic metabolites produced by microscopic mold fungi that contaminate grain crops both during vegetation and storage and processing of feed. The main producers of mycotoxins dangerous for poultry farming are fungi of the genera *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Penicillium* [3]. Consumption of contaminated feed negatively affects metabolism, immune status, and productivity of poultry, causing liver and

kidney damage, reproductive disorders, and, in some cases, mortality [4].

Particular attention should be paid to the effect of mycotoxins on the functional state of the digestive tract and intestinal microbiome. Toxicants directly damage the intestinal mucosa, disrupt nutrient absorption, and alter the composition of intestinal microbiocenosis [5-7].

The normal intestinal microflora of poultry is represented by a complex association of facultative and obligate anaerobic microorganisms, among which lactobacilli, bifidobacteria, bacteroides, and other representatives of commensal microbiota play an important role [8]. Disturbance of the dynamic balance of intestinal microbiocenosis is accompanied by the development of dysbiosis, gastroenteritis, and enteritis, resulting in impaired feed conversion, decreased body weight gain, and reduced poultry productivity [9]. Changes in the qualitative and quantitative composition of intesti-

nal microflora are considered one of the key pathogenic mechanisms in the development of intoxication and metabolic disorders in poultry [10-12].

In this regard, the search for effective means of feed detoxification and reduction of the negative impact of mycotoxins on poultry is highly relevant. Modern approaches are increasingly focused on the use of environmentally safe enterosorbents and natural adsorbents capable of binding toxic compounds in the digestive tract and reducing manifestations of oxidative stress [13-15].

A promising direction in poultry farming is the use of natural mineral enterosorbents, particularly zeolites and aluminosilicates, characterized by high adsorption and ion-exchange capacity and capable of effectively binding toxic compounds in the poultry digestive tract without significantly disturbing the balance of vitamins and trace elements [16, 17].

Along with traditional zeolites and bentonites, Cambrian blue clay attracts considerable interest as a natural aluminosilicate mineral rich in silicon, magnesium, iron, and other trace elements. Due to pronounced adsorption and ion-exchange properties, such minerals are able to bind toxic compounds and metabolic products, reducing the toxic load on the poultry organism. In addition, their use may positively affect mineral metabolism, digestion processes, and contribute to stabilization of intestinal microbiocenosis [18, 19].

However, the influence of Cambrian clay specifically on the dynamics of intestinal microbiocenosis and metabolic status of chickens under consumption of feed contaminated by biotic factors requires further investigation.

The aim of the study was to investigate the state of intestinal microbiocenosis and the characteristics of biochemical blood parameters in chickens fed feed contaminated by biotic factors and to evaluate the effectiveness of Cambrian clay as a corrective agent.

Materials and methods

The studies were conducted at the Laboratory of Epizootology, Parasitology, Monitoring of Animal Diseases and Providing of the Odesa Research Station of the National Scientific Center "Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine" (NSC "IECVM"), as well as at the Laboratory of Clinical Biochemistry and the Laboratory for the Study of Swine Diseases of the NSC "IECVM".

The experiment lasted 35 days and was carried out on 45-day-old Redbro chickens ($n = 10$). Three groups of poultry were formed according to the analogue principle. Chickens of Group I (control) received standard complete feed (SCF). The diet of Group II (experimental) consisted of 85% high-quality SCF and 15%

low-toxic feed (LTF). Chickens of Group III (experimental) received 85% high-quality SCF, 15% LTF, and an additional 1% Cambrian clay.

Feed toxicity was determined according to DSTU 3570-97 (1999) using a bioassay on the test organism *Colpoda steinii*. Mycological studies revealed contamination of feed with micromycetes of the genera *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* [20].

To evaluate intestinal microbiocenosis and determine the degree of dysbiosis, classical microbiological methods were used. Fresh poultry feces served as the material for investigation. The quantitative composition of the main representatives of obligate and opportunistic microflora, including *Lactobacillus* spp., *Bifidobacterium* spp., *Enterococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Clostridium* spp., and other opportunistic microorganisms, was determined in the collected samples. The degree of dysbiosis was assessed by a decrease in lactobacilli and bifidobacteria, an increase in opportunistic microflora, and disturbance of the ratio between obligate and facultative microbiota [6, 7].

To evaluate the functional state of chickens, biochemical blood serum parameters characterizing protein, enzymatic, and metabolic homeostasis were studied. Blood samples were collected from the wing vein in the morning before feeding. Blood was collected into dry tubes and kept at room temperature until clot formation, followed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Blood serum was used for further biochemical analyses.

Biochemical parameters were determined using standard methods with reagent kits produced by "Filisit-Diagnostics" (Ukraine) on a Stat Fax 1904 Plus biochemical analyzer (USA). The following indicators were determined in blood serum: total protein by the biuret method; albumins using bromocresol green reaction; globulins by calculation method (difference between total protein and albumins); ALT and AST activity by the Reitman–Frankel method [21]; uric acid by enzymatic method; circulating immune complexes by the Khavkina method; serglycoids by the orcinol reaction according to the Orlov method.

Clinical and productive indicators were additionally recorded, including feces consistency, frequency of diarrhea manifestations, feed conversion, body weight gain, and survival rate.

Mathematical analysis of the obtained data was performed using Microsoft Excel software (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington, USA) by calculating the arithmetic mean (M), standard error (m), and significance level (p) using one-way ANOVA with Fisher's criterion [22].

Research results. According to clinical and productive indicators, feeding 45-day-old chickens with a diet containing 15% low-toxic feed for 35 days negatively affected poultry productivity (Table 1).

Table 1.

Effect of low-toxic feed and Cambrian clay on productive performance of chickens (M±m, n = 10)

Parameters	Group I, control	Group II, experimental	Group III, experimental
Initial body weight, g	7340 ± 0.13	7340 ± 0.11	7340 ± 0.12
Final body weight, g	11200 ± 0.18	8600 ± 0.09	10950 ± 0.14
Average daily gain at the end of the experiment, g	110.28	36.00	103.14
Average daily feed intake, g	240	320	250
Feed conversion ratio	3.2	5.1	3.4

At the end of the experiment, body weight in chickens of Group II was 23.21% lower compared with the control, while average daily gain decreased 3.06-fold. At the same time, average daily feed intake increased by 33.3%, and feed conversion worsened 1.59-fold, indicating reduced efficiency of nutrient utilization under toxic load.

Supplementation of the diet with Cambrian clay (Group III) improved productive performance of chickens. At the end of the experiment, body weight in this group was only 2.23% lower than in the control, while average daily gain differed by only 6.92%. Feed conversion ratio in Group III was 1.5 times lower compared with Group II and approached the values of healthy poultry. The obtained results indicate the ability

of Cambrian clay to partially neutralize the negative effects of low-toxic feed on growth intensity and feed utilization efficiency.

Thus, feeding low-toxic feed caused pronounced growth suppression in chickens, reduced average daily gains, and worsened feed conversion. Inclusion of Cambrian clay into the diet significantly reduced the negative impact of toxic feed, which manifested as improved growth intensity and feed utilization efficiency.

During evaluation of intestinal microbiocenosis in chickens of Group I, it was established that the qualitative and quantitative composition of microflora corresponded to indicators characteristic of healthy poultry (Table 2).

Table 2.

Effect of low-toxic feed and Cambrian clay on microbiota of the large intestine in chickens (CFU/g)

Microorganisms	Group I, control	Group II, experimental	Group III, experimental
<i>E. coli</i>	35 × 10 ⁸	48 × 10 ⁸	38 × 10 ⁸
<i>Proteus</i>	28 × 10 ⁸	42 × 10 ⁸	31 × 10 ⁸
<i>Enterococcus</i>	13 × 10 ⁸	16 × 10 ⁸	14 × 10 ⁸
<i>Clostridium</i>	17 × 10 ⁸	41 × 10 ⁸	30 × 10 ⁸
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	22 × 10 ⁸	39 × 10 ⁸	33 × 10 ⁸
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	3 × 10 ⁵	36 × 10 ⁶	28 × 10 ⁶
<i>Candida albicans</i>	2 × 10 ³	14 × 10 ⁵	9 × 10 ⁵
<i>Lactobacillus</i>	4 × 10 ⁵	–	–
<i>Bifidobacterium</i>	8 × 10 ⁵	–	–

Feeding low-toxic feed caused pronounced disturbances in microbiocenosis of the large intestine in chickens. In poultry of Group II, the amount of *E. coli* increased 1.37-fold, *Proteus* – 1.5-fold, *Clostridium* – 2.41-fold, and *Staphylococcus* – 1.77-fold compared with the control group. The most pronounced changes were observed for *Bacillus cereus* and *Candida albicans*, whose counts increased 120- and 700-fold, respectively.

At the same time, chickens of Group II showed complete suppression of obligate intestinal microflora – *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* were absent in the examined samples, indicating the development of severe dysbiosis under toxic load.

Supplementation of the diet with Cambrian clay (Group III) contributed to partial normalization of intestinal microbiota. Compared with Group II, the amount of *E. coli* decreased 1.26-fold, *Proteus* – 1.35-fold, *Clostridium* – 1.37-fold, *Staphylococcus* – 1.18-fold, *Bacillus cereus* – 1.29-fold, and *Candida albicans* – 1.56-fold. The obtained results indicate the ability of Cambrian clay to reduce the level of opportunistic microflora and partially stabilize intestinal microbiocenosis in chickens.

The next stage of the study involved investigation of biochemical blood serum parameters in chickens to evaluate the state of protein, enzymatic, and metabolic homeostasis under different feeding conditions (Table 3).

Table 3.

Biochemical blood serum parameters of chickens under feeding with low-toxic feed and Cambrian clay supplementation (M±m, n = 5)

Parameters	Group I, control	Group II, experimental	Group III, experimental
Total protein, g/L	46.80±0.98	40.76±1.02***	44.58±1.16***
Albumins, g/L	19.28±1.32	19.34±0.06***	19.68±0.34***
Globulins, g/L	27.52±1.14	21.42±0.76***	24.90±1.34***
A/G ratio	0.70±0.04	0.90±0.02	0.79±0.02
ALT, mmol/L·h	0.50±0.006	0.80±0.007**	0.62±0.02*
AST, mmol/L·h	2.52±0.004	2.10±0.002***	2.22±0.02***
Uric acid, mmol/L	0.282±0.05	0.326±0.03***	0.318±0.03***
Creatinine, µmol/L	26.44±0.48	30.19±0.36	29.45±0.05
Triglycerides, µmol/L	1.29±0.02***	1.49±0.07***	1.28±0.06***
Cholesterol, µmol/L	1.47±0.08***	2.32±0.04***	1.67±0.02***
Total calcium, µmol/L	2.25±0.008***	2.66±0.004***	2.28±0.07***
Inorganic phosphorus, µmol/L	1.48±0.02***	1.29±0.003***	1.33±0.004***

*Note: * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001 compared with the control group.

Feeding chickens with low-toxic feed was accompanied by pronounced changes in biochemical blood serum parameters, indicating disturbances in protein, lipid, and mineral metabolism.

Compared with the control, chickens of Group II showed a 12.9% decrease in total protein concentration and a 22.2% decrease in globulin levels, indicating suppression of protein-synthesizing function and decreased immunological reactivity. Simultaneously, the A/G ratio increased by 28.6%, indicating the development of dysproteinemia.

Metabolic disturbances were characterized by increased concentrations of uric acid by 15.6%, creatinine by 14.2%, triglycerides by 15.5%, and cholesterol by 57.8% compared with the control group. ALT activity in Group II chickens increased by 60.0%, whereas AST activity decreased by 16.7%. In addition, total calcium concentration increased by 18.2%, while inorganic phosphorus decreased by 12.8%.

In chickens of Group III supplemented with Cambrian clay, most biochemical parameters were closer to control values. Total protein concentration was only 4.7% lower than in the control, while globulins were 9.5% lower. The A/G ratio exceeded control values by 12.9%. Cholesterol levels were 13.6% higher than in the control, triglycerides practically did not differ from the control, while uric acid concentration exceeded control values by 12.8%. ALT activity was 24.0% higher than in the control, whereas AST activity remained 11.9% lower. At the same time, total calcium concentration exceeded control values by only 1.3%, and inorganic phosphorus remained 10.1% lower.

Compared with Group II, supplementation with Cambrian clay promoted partial normalization of protein, lipid, and mineral metabolism, which was manifested by increased concentrations of total protein and globulins and decreased cholesterol, triglycerides, and ALT activity.

The obtained results indicate the ability of Cambrian clay to reduce the severity of metabolic disorders caused by feeding low-toxic feed.

Conclusions

1. Feeding chickens with a diet containing 15% low-toxic feed for 35 days caused a decrease in body

weight, average daily gain, and feed conversion efficiency, and was accompanied by the development of intestinal dysbiosis characterized by an increase in opportunistic microflora and suppression of obligate microorganisms (*Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*).

2. Toxic feed load was accompanied by disturbances in protein, lipid, and mineral metabolism, manifested by decreased total protein and globulins and increased cholesterol, triglycerides, uric acid, and ALT activity.

3. Inclusion of 1% Cambrian clay in the diet improved productive performance, partially normalized intestinal microbiocenosis, and stabilized biochemical blood parameters in chickens, indicating the prospects of its use as a natural enterosorbent.

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